

(Found : C, 73.15 ; H, 10.12. $C_{12}H_{20}O_2$ calcd. for : C, 73.43 ; H, 10.27%) ; ν_{max} 3 000–2 950, 1 725, 1 650, 1 620, 1 450, 1 230, 1 045, 1 005 and 980 cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 0.8–1.1 (3H, t, CH_3), 1.2–1.6 (9H, m, saturated methylene and OCH_2CH_3), 2.1 (2H, m, allylic methylene), 4.3 (2H, m, $-\text{CO}-\text{O}-\text{CH}_2-$), 5.85 (1H, d, J 15.0 Hz, 2-H), 6.25 (1H, m, 4-H) and 6.9–7.5 (2H, m, 3-H and 5-H).

2E,4E-Decadien-1-oiic acid (7) : To a methanolic solution (40 ml) of the ester (6 ; 1 g, 5.10 mmol) was added a saturated solution of KOH (0.3 g, 5.36 mmol) in methanol and the contents were stirred for 10 h at room temperature. The alcohol was then evaporated, the residue treated with water (20 ml) and extracted with ether. The aqueous layer was then acidified with hydrochloric acid and extracted with ether (6 \times 30 ml). The combined ether extract was dried and the solvent evaporated to furnish the unsaturated acid (7 ; 0.68 g, 70%) (Found : C, 71.16 ; H, 9.41. $C_{10}H_{16}O_2$ calcd. for : C, 71.39 ; H, 9.59%) ; ν_{max} 3 000–3 400, 1 700, 1 645, 1 620, 1 420, 1 280, 1 000 and 730 cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 0.9 (3H, t, CH_3), 1.32 (6H, m, saturated methylenes), 2.1–2.2 (2H, m, allylic methylene), 5.85 (1H, d, J 15 Hz, 2-H), 6.25 (1H, m, 4-H), 6.9–7.6 (2H, m, 3-H and 5-H) and 10.8 (1H, s, COOH).

N-(2E,4E-Decadienoyl)pyrrolidine (2) : To a solution of 7 (0.4 g, 2.38 mmol), the pyrrolidine (0.154 g, 2.17 mmol) and triethylamine (0.437 g, 4.33 mmol) in dry CH_2Cl_2 (50 ml) at 0°, was added dropwise $POCl_3$ (0.365 g, 2.38 mmol) in CH_2Cl_2 (5 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred for 2 h at 0° and another 1 h at room temperature. The contents were then poured in cold water and the organic layer separated, washed with saturated $NaHCO_3$ solution, water and dried. Evaporation of the solvent followed by chromatographic purification of the residue over silica gel afforded the pure amide (2 ; 0.3 g, 56%) (tlc single spot) (Found : C, 75.78 ; H, 10.29 ; N, 5.91. $C_{14}H_{23}NO$ calcd. for : C, 75.97 ; H, 10.47 ; N, 6.33%) ; ν_{max} 2 950, 2 940, 1 650, 1 630, 1 605, 1 440, 1 005 and 980 cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 0.85 (3H, m, CH_3), 1.2–1.5 (6H, m, saturated methylenes), 1.79–2.02 (6H, m, allylic methylene and β,β' -hydrogens), 3.4–3.6 (4H, m, α and α' -hydrogens), 6.0 (1H, d, J 15 Hz, 2-H), 6.1–6.24 (2H, m, 4-H and 5-H) and 7.2 (1H, m, 3-H).

N-Isobutyl-(2E,4E-decadienamamide (1) : It was prepared in a similar way as 2 using the acid 7 (0.60 g, 3.57 mmol), isobutylamine (0.24 g, 3.29 mmol), triethylamine (0.66 g, 6.53 mmol) in dry CH_2Cl_2 and $POCl_3$ (0.55 g, 3.58 mmol). Usual work up and chromatographic purification of the residue afforded the amide (1 ; 0.5 g, 67%) (Found : C, 75.04 ; H, 11.14 ; N, 5.96. $C_{14}H_{25}NO$ calcd. for : C, 75.28 ; H, 11.28 ; N, 6.27%) ; ν_{max} 3 070, 3 000, 1 655, 1 625, 1 550, 1 265, 1 005, 790 and 770 cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 0.9 (9H, m, CH_3 , $CH(CH_3)_2$), 1.32 (6H, m, saturated methylenes), 1.8–2.2 (3H, m, allylic methylene and $CH_2CH(CH_3)_2$), 3.1–3.3 (2H, t, $NHCH_2$), 5.5 (1H, br s, NH), 6.0 (1H, d, J 15.0 Hz,

2-H), 6.2 (2H, m, 4-H and 5-H) and 7.27 (1H, m, 3-H).

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A New Synthesis of Polychlorobibenzyls†

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COUPLING reactions of alkyl halides under homogeneous and heterogeneous conditions are well-known¹⁻⁴. Diarylmethane dihalides (Ar_2CX_2) have been converted to tetraaryl alkenes ($Ar_2C=CAr_2$) with sodium selenide⁵ and iron pentacarbonyl⁶. 4-Nitrobenzyl chloride with potassium *t*-butoxide undergoes oxidative coupling to give 4,4'-dinitrostilbene via nucleophilic substitution followed by elimination⁷. With metallic iron⁸, copper⁹ and colloidal palladium¹⁰, benzotrichloride gives tetrachlorobibenzyl in aqueous medium. In this communication we report a new reagent sodium iodide which can couple activated alkyl halides to give polychlorobibenzyls.

Experimental

The coupling reaction was carried out by refluxing the alkyl chloride (α,α,α -trichlorotoluene or α,α -dichlorotoluene ; 10 mmol) in *N,N*-dimethylformamide or acetonitrile or 2-propanol (50 ml), with sodium iodide (50 mmol) for 1–4 h. The refluxate on dilution with water followed by decolourisation with sodium thiosulphate yielded the solid product which was crystallised from alcohol-chloroform mixture (1 : 1).

Results and Discussion

The reaction of activated polyhalide with iodide is presented in Scheme 1. There are two possible

†Part of this work was presented at the 7th. Annual Conference of the Indian Council of Chemists, Gwalior, 1987.

Scheme 1

reaction modes. Nucleophilic substitution of Cl⁻ by I⁻ in compound 1 (R=H) will lead to 2, which in turn can form 7 (R=H) through the carbanion 4 or can form 6 or 8 (R=H) through the carbenoids 3 and 5, respectively. Compounds 6 and 8 were not produced, since the tests for unsaturation were negative. The appearance of a signal at δ 4.8 in the ¹H nmr spectrum of the product supported the structure 7.

The reaction of I⁻ with α,α,α-trichlorotoluene is more facile than that with α,α-dichlorotoluene and yields a greater amount of the coupled product (Table 1). Moreover, the reaction time is less in dipolar aprotic solvents (DMF, CH₃CN) than in 2-propanol.

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd.	M p °C	Yield %/(Reaction time).		
		D M F.	Aceto- nitrile	2-Pro- panol
C ₆ H ₅ CCl ₂ -Cl ₂ CC ₆ H ₅	160	75 (1.0)	70 (1.25)	72 (2.0)
C ₆ H ₅ CHCl-ClHCC ₆ H ₅	189	50 (1.5)	45 (3.0)	40 (4.0)

*The elemental analyses values are in good agreement with the calculated values.

With α-chloro- and α-bromotoluenes, only α-iodotoluene is obtained and no coupling reaction is observed. Other systems like CH₂Cl₂, CHCl₃, CCl₄ and their bromo and iodo analogues failed to react. Hence we conclude that this coupling reaction is highly specific in nature and occurs only when there is more than one halogen substituent on the same carbon along with a phenyl group, which activates the system.

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A New Route for the Synthesis of Benzofuro-[3,2-g][1]benzopyran-2(H)-one

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THE biological activities of linear furocoumarins known as psoralens are well-known. Psoralen, 8-methoxypsoralen and the trimethyl analogue, trioxsalen are effective photochemotherapeutic agents in the treatment of psoriasis¹. However, they react with DNA by bifunctional mode and are shown to be mutagenic when used in combination with UV-A irradiation². They were also found to be carcinogenic in mice³. Thus monofunctionalised psoralen derivatives are considered safer and it was therefore thought of interest to synthesise benzofuro-[3,2-g][1]benzopyran-2(H)-one and its methyl derivative, a monofunctionalised psoralen by a new route using the technique of tosyloxylation and detosyloxylation. Previously the same compound was synthesised from 7-hydroxycoumarin⁴.

2,4-Dihydroxy acetophenone (1a), on condensation with 2-bromocyclohexanone in presence of potassium carbonate gave 4-(cyclohexan-2-onyloxy)-2-hydroxyacetophenone (2a) which on cyclisation with 0.1 N alcoholic potassium hydroxide solution gave 5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-2-hydroxy-3-acetyldibenzofuran (3a) (Scheme 1). Formation of 3a can be explained on the basis of intramolecular aldol condensation⁴. The phenoxide ion (2a) attacks the exocyclic carbonyl group through the carbanion generated at *para*-position to the phenoxide ion to give 2b followed by abstraction of the proton at the ring junction to regenerate phenoxide ion (2c),

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